

58 years of Urban Streambank Stability: Sherman Creek Reach at County Club Drive, Duval County, Atlantic Beach, Florida

29 April 2017

Submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements of
575.730 Geomorphic and Ecologic Foundations of Stream Restoration
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Abstract

This work examines the 58-year stability of the Left bank of Sherman Creek reach (a natural soil bank with a healthy riparian zone) using a modified Lane's Balance relationship. Sherman Creek is a second order urban stream (FL WBID 2227) which has become a component in a municipal drainage system. The Right bank's original soil material with riparian zone and floodplain have all been removed and replaced with an engineered revetment. Historical aerial photographs obtained from state and Federal sources were reviewed bank to bank to circa 1956/1957, and measurements were made of the width of the reach to detect erosion, one key component of the modified Lane's Balance. No changes in reach width were detected over the 58 years of record. It was concluded that the persistent, healthy, and dense riparian zone (trees, vegetation, palms) on the Left bank is a likely reason for the Left bank stability. It is recommended that the healthy riparian zone of the Left bank be protected, and a minor 50 ft² area with no riparian vegetation showing signs of erosion instability be restored, to maximize future stability of the Left bank. Expected continued reduction of natural pervious surfaces from urban growth and development in the watershed will increase the volume of stormwater discharge to Sherman Creek reach, increasing the risks of erosion of the Left bank.

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Introduction

This paper documents a unique stream bank stability analysis of a specific reach of Sherman Creek. Based on an extensive search of stream science literature and numerous communications with state and local government officials no analysis of this type has been performed on the reach of Sherman Creek located near Country Club Drive.

This paper examines fundamental details underlying the persistent (left) bank stability of a reach of Sherman Creek (State of Florida, Water Body ID = 2227) located in Duval County, Atlantic Beach, Florida (**Figure 1** and **Figure 2**; see also **Appendix A** – Aerial Photographs). Sherman Creek is a second order stream which drains into the St. Johns River located in northeast Florida.

Figure 1 – General Site Location

(Source: Final TMDL for Sherman Creek, FDEP, 2008)

Figure 2 – Sherman Creek Reach

(Source: USGS and Florida Department of Transportation, 2011)

Research Question

Why has Sherman Creek (specifically, the Left-bank of the reach at Country Club Drive) not enlarged (eroded, in width) over its 58 years of record?

Background

As an urban watershed is developed, the extent of impervious surface increases, increasing the volume of surface runoff to urban streams (Bledsoe and Watson, 2001; USDA, 1986). When combined with expected decreases in watershed sediment yield (through reduced erosion of natural areas), stream enlargement can result through widening and/or deepening, or both. In a landmark analysis (Lane, 1955) published the conceptual relationships between the capacity of a channel to carry discharge (Q_w), sediment discharge or load (Q_s), streambed slope (S), and streambed sediment size (D_s). Known as Lane's Relation, it is useful for understanding some stream morphodynamics. Lane's Relation is defined (Lane, 1955):

$$Q_w S \propto Q_s D_s \quad (1)$$

However, Lane's Relation it did not explicitly include the effects of changes in stream width (w) and/or depth (d). Building on Lane's earlier work, Dust and Wohl (2012) extended the Lane Relation to explicitly include stream width (w) and depth (d), as defined below.

$$Q_s \propto \frac{Q_w S}{D_s} \left(\frac{w}{d}\right)^{-1} \quad (2)$$

$$\therefore Q_w S \propto Q_s D_s \left(\frac{w}{d}\right) \quad (3)$$

Equation (3) of Dust and Wohl (2012) indicates that the ability of a stream to move water within a streambed slope is proportional to the sediment load (Q_s), sediment size (D_s) times the ratio of channel width and depth (w/d).

If we assume D_s and Q_s are low and essentially constant for an urban stream in a highly-developed area, then equation (3) becomes:

$$Q_w S \propto \left(\frac{w}{d}\right) \quad (4)$$

Further, if bed slope (S) is unchanging (constant) (as is observable in coastal areas of low to no topographic relief, and fine-grain streambed sediments, e.g., clay dominated), then equation (4) simplifies to:

$$Q_w \propto \left(\frac{w}{d}\right) \quad (5)$$

Equation (5) represents that stream discharge (Q_w) is proportional to the ratio of stream width and stream depth.

Equation (5) describes an important relationship; as stream discharge increases (for example, as would be expected during a stormwater runoff event), the channel width to depth ratio would be expected to change (through erosion) and/or the stream would exceed bank full stage and flow into its floodplain.

Reach Description and History

In this reach of Sherman Creek the Right bank floodplain no longer exists; connection there to the floodplain is completely cut due to the presence of a engineered revetment; however, the Left bank consists of natural soil with a healthy riparian zone and complete connection to its floodplain.

Field Reconnaissance

On April 13, 2017 a field reconnaissance was conducted by Gary D. Moore to the Sherman Creek reach at Country Club Drive (see **Appendix A** – Aerial Photographs; **Appendix B** – Site Reconnaissance Photographs; **Appendix C** – Stream Visual Assessment Checklist and Site Score; **Appendix D** – Field Reconnaissance Notebook Pages). The following is a summary of important observations made during the field visit:

- The local weather on April 13, 2017 was mostly sunny with the ambient temperature around 70 degrees Fahrenheit.
- A vertical masonry wall (engineered revetment) was present where the Right bank used to be; the wall completely cuts the connection between the stream and its floodplain.
- The Left bank was heavily vegetated including several mature hardwood trees, palms, and extensive undergrowth.
- The Left bank showed no major signs of erosion. With one exception: a limited area (approximately 50 feet square) located southeast corner of the Left bank (see Photograph Nos. 13 and 14, **Appendix B**).
- Stream flow exhibited low to no flow.
- Stream water clarity was extremely poor (very cloudy).
- In most locations of the Reach the bottom could not be seen but appeared to be less than 5 feet deep.
- The reach of Sherman Creek under investigation is located near the headwaters of the stream.
- No fish or other aquatic life was observed.
- Limited areas of surface algae growth were observed.

Stream Visual Assessment Protocol (United States Department of Agriculture, Natural Resources Conservation Service)

A visual assessment of Sherman Creek reach was performed by Gary D. Moore during the field visit using the Stream Visual Assessment Protocol developed by the United States Department of Agriculture, Natural Resources Conservation Service, National Water and Climate Center Technical Note 99-1.

- A score of **3.8** was recorded, which is indicative of the poor condition of Sherman Creek reach. Scores greater than 9 indicate excellent health.

See **Appendix C** for Stream Visual Assessment Checklist and Site Score.

Sherman Creek Reach History

In circa 1956/1957 Sherman Creek's channel was modified to drain wetlands for mosquito control to help protect the health of nearby residents in the growing urban areas. Eventually Sherman Creek became the major stormwater drainage conveyance for the City of Atlantic Beach, including the Selva Marina County Club (now the Atlantic Beach Country Club) (**Appendix F**, historical documentation). As such, Sherman Creek, once a natural stream, is now an urban stream that receives runoff from adjacent paved streets and from a much broader area across the City via linked drainage ditches and culverts. The City of Atlantic Beach, an area that has and continues to experience a strong building/redevelopment sector (i.e., 185 new, replacement homes since 2014) (City of Atlantic Beach, personal communications, 2017). The latest information from the City of Atlantic Beach, Public Works Department, indicates much of the municipality is at approximately 50 percent (2017) impervious surface, and 200+ homes to be constructed at the nearby Atlantic Beach Country Club are permitted for as much as 65 percent impervious surface per home lot (City of Atlantic Beach, personal communications, 2017). Based on this information, stormwater runoff volume to Sherman Creek reach is anticipated to increase.

Study Approach

To investigate the change in the width (from erosion, if any) of Sherman Creek reach since it was developed in circa 1956/1957, low-altitude aerial photographs documenting the 53 years of stream activity were analyzed and the reach width measured. Specifically, aerial photographs for the years 1963, 1970, 1980, 1994, 2014, and 2016 were used in for the analysis (obtained from Federal, state archives) (**Appendix A**). To overcome photographic scale uncertainty, for example, changes in camera / lens technologies, differing flight paths/ altitudes, and so on, any of which can complicate credible measurement (of stream width) for the period of analysis, a feature of known length visible in all of the photographs was used for scale, i.e., a swimming pool 100 feet in length, constructed circa 1956/1957 and located at the adjacent Atlantic Beach Country Club (see **Appendix E** for pool measurement documentation).

As the stormwater runoff quantity increases (as is expected with a developing urban watershed) equation 5 of the modified Lane's Balance indicates that Sherman Creek reach should respond by either channel widening and/or deepening, or both. Surprisingly, no major changes in reach width (as measured approximately from North to South) were detected in the aerial photographs reviewed, despite ever increasing discharge to the reach from urban stormwater runoff. Although the aerial photographs provide only a two-dimensional view of reach history, based on the extent of the water body, long established and relatively unchanging streets and buildings in the area, it appears that significant deepening of the reach channel has not occurred.

No evidence of excessive sediment supply during the 58-year history of the reach was apparent in the aerial photographs reviewed, i.e., no accumulations of sediment were visible along the stream course.

It appears likely, therefore, a major reason for the persistent, 58-year stability of the Left bank of Sherman Creek is a healthy riparian zone (see **Appendix B**, Site Reconnaissance Photographs). This zone of trees and vegetation has consistently been present during all except the early initial years of reach development.

Results

- Based on equation 5 (modified Lane's Balance), changes in the width of Sherman Creek were anticipated to be visible in the historical aerial photographs analyzed. However, no changes in reach width were discovered
- Given the headwater location of Sherman Creek reach:
 - Except in times of intense precipitation, e.g., major storms, hurricanes, Sherman Creek reach receive little, if any, surface runoff. Rather the channel's water level is maintained by groundwater (baseflow). During these majority quiescent periods, the stream discharge rate is extremely slow.
 - Similarly, the sediment supply to the reach is extremely limited, occurring only during times of intense precipitation, and limited to the fine grain materials contained in urban runoff.
 - No visual evidence on historical aerial photographs was discovered of excess sediment supply to Sherman Creek, i.e., no accumulations of sediment were visible along the stream course.
- Despite the requirements of the modified Lane's Balance the Left bank showed no major signs of erosion. With one exception: a limited area (approximately 50 feet square) showing contemporary signs of erosion possibility due to a non-vegetated area of limited extent located southeast corner of the Left bank (see **Appendix B**, Photograph Nos. 13 and 14,).

Conclusions

- To avoid erosion and maximize future stability of the Left bank of Sherman Creek reach, a riparian zone with a healthy assemblage of trees and vegetation should be maintained.
- The limited 50 foot² area of no riparian vegetation on the Left bank (**Appendix B**, Photograph No. 13 and 14) should be remediated with planting of like kind vegetation and trees. Once planted, these areas should be nurtured and protected to ensure successful growth and continued stability of the Left bank.
- Expected continued reduction of natural pervious surfaces from urban growth and development in the watershed will increase the volume of stormwater discharge to Sherman Creek reach, increasing the risks of erosion of the Left bank.

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Appendix A
Aerial Photographs

Gayton

1963

Source: Low USGS Aerial
Photographic Archive

Reach View - 1963

(90)

Gary D. Moore

1970

Reach width View - 1970

gd

Gary Moore

1980

Reach Width View-1980

(gde)

Handwritten signature

1994

Image U.S. Geological Survey

Google Earth

Google Earth

feet
meters

Beach View - 1994

900

Stan DM

2014

Google Earth

Google Earth

Realt View - 2014

Graydon

2016

Google Earth

Google Earth

feet
meters

2016

Appendix B
Site Reconnaissance Photographs

Photograph No. 1 – Sherman Creek Reach at County Club Drive (view from the northwest looking southeast)

Photograph No. 2 – Left bank (center) Sherman Creek Reach (view from north looking south)

Photograph No. 3 – View looking southeast from Right bank revetment; Left bank and stormwater discharge point to Sherman Creek reach visible (center)

Photograph No. 4 – Close up of stormwater discharge point to Sherman Creek reach.

Photograph No. 5 – Right bank revetment, Sherman Creek Reach (view from southeast looking northwest).

Photograph No. 6 – Heavily vegetated Left bank, Sherman Creek reach; stormwater discharge point embankment visible on left.

Photograph No. 7 – Atlantic Beach Country Club parking lot, located immediately north of Sherman Creek reach, Atlantic Beach Drive in foreground (view looking north from top of Left bank revetment).

Photograph No. 8 – View look south along Selva Marina Drive from Atlantic Beach Drive; street drainage / stormwater discharge point to Sherman Creek reach visible (center, right); intersection with Country Club Drive visible (center, left)

Photograph No. 9 – View looking north along Selva Marine Drive from street-level discharge point to Sherman Creek reach.

Photograph No. 10 – Close up view of street-level discharge / drainage structure to Sherman Creek reach. The drainage structure is located at the northwest corner of Selva Marina Drive and Country Club Drive.

Photograph No. 11 – Street-level drainage view to Sherman Creek reach; intersection of Selva Marina Drive and Country Club Drive (center).

Photograph No. 12 – Street-level drainage view to Sherman Creek reach (view looking south along Selva Marina Drive).

Photograph No. 13 – View of suspected erosion of Left bank; street-level drain concrete embankment visible in foreground.

Photograph No. 14 – Close up of suspected Left bank erosion depicted in Photograph No. 13 above.

Appendix C
Stream Visual Assessment Protocol Checklist and Site Score

Stream Visual Assessment Protocol

Owners name State of Florida Evaluator's name G. Moore Date 13 April 17

Stream name Sherman Creek (Reach at Waterbody ID number WBID = 2227

Reach location Country Club) Southwest corner of Atlantic Beach Drive and Selva Marina Drive.

Ecoregion _____ Drainage area 6.45 mi² Gradient _____

Applicable reference site _____

Land use within drainage (%): row crop hayland grazing/pasture forest ~15 residential ~34
 confined animal feeding operations Cons. Reserve industrial ~12 Other: ~39

Weather conditions-today Sunny Past 2-5 days _____

Active channel width ~80 feet** Dominant substrate: boulder _____ gravel _____ sand Minor silt mud

***estimated from Google Earth, 2016 Digital Globe images.*

* Data from Table 104 (pg. 222) of Lower St. Johns Tributary Basin, Basin Management Action Plan, State of Florida, 2010. Data are from 2004.

Assessment Scores

Channel condition	2
Hydrologic alteration	2
Riparian zone	2
Bank stability	7
Water appearance	1
Nutrient enrichment	5
Barriers to fish movement	10
Instream fish cover	1

(only 1/2 of reach has healthy zone)
 (1/2 bank is an engineered wall; 1/2 bank appears stable with healthy veg)
 (some algal growth; cannot see bottom)

Pools	NA
Invertebrate habitat	4

Not accessible; visual review shows no evidence of pools. bottom not visible due to poor water clarity.

Score only if applicable	
Canopy cover	<input type="checkbox"/>
Manure presence	<input type="checkbox"/>
Salinity	<input type="checkbox"/>
Rifle embeddedness	<input type="checkbox"/>
Macroinvertebrates Observed (optional)	<input type="checkbox"/>

1/2 of reach has riparian habitat.
 $\Sigma = 34 \div 9$ (categories)
 ≈ 3.8

Overall score (Total divided by number scored)	<u>3.8</u>	<6.0	Poor
		6.1-7.4	Fair
		7.5-8.9	Good
		>9.0	Excellent

Suspected causes of observed problems Development on left bank of creek
(Atlantic Beach Country Club) has completely separated the creek
from its floodplain.

Recommendations Crucial to maintain healthy riparian zone, vegetation
on the right bank to mitigate erosion risk.

Appendix D
Field Reconnaissance Logbook Pages

Shoeman Creek @ County 17
 Study (Atlantic Beach, FL)
 Stream Segment Survey

6-10:00 AM

Weather: Mostly Sunny, 70's

Hypothesis: Reach dynamics put the south bank at risk of flooding.

Observation of south bank.

- Bankfull conditions are not present today.
- The riparian area has one mature tree (60') and several smaller trees, palms and mossy brush. A cross-section is provided below.

The riparian vegetation and trees look healthy and the density is robust.

gdm

Shoeman Creek @ County 13 April 11
 Study (Atlantic Beach, FL)
 Stream Segment Survey

Country Club Parking

Shoeman Creek

Riparian Properties

- (A) Storm water inlet, dual system, 1) sand and water through ramp and, 2) discharge pipe. Concrete showing signs of weathering.
- (B) Partially submerged, algal growth evident. A lot of coral accumulation.
- (C) Storm water outlet, partly submerged, ~ 2' diameter.

gdm

Appendix E
Pool Measurement Documentation

Garrett

18/04/17 @

Appendix F
Historical Documentation – Sherman Creek Channel Modification; Wetland
Destruction

man & Doug Sanders, Greater Jacksonville Open 1966

Arnold Palmer 1962

Selva Marina Country Club was steeped in First Coast golf history. It was the original home to what would become The Players Championship, which was then known as The Greater Jacksonville Open, before the tournament was moved to Ponte Vedra Beach. Selva Marina hosted The Greater Jacksonville Open in 1965-66.

In May of 1955 Mr. Harcourt Bull, Jr. called a meeting among his 30 closest friends in the City Hall of Atlantic Beach to discuss entertainment in Atlantic Beach. Mr. Bull was hoping to inspire his group to create a club – golf, tennis, swimming, an airstrip, and maybe even boating– which would, of course, be the center of the social lives of Beach Area residents. Hoping the existence of such an establishment might inspire a housing boom in the area, Mr. Bull entered the meeting with a resoluteness he was well known for possessing. The idea took hold rapidly and plans to make it a reality followed swiftly.

Locations for this vision were discussed. As Atlantic Beach had one golf course in its past, the location of that original course was a logical starting point. RCBS Corporation, a company owned by the Bull family held deed to much of the land in Atlantic Beach. Mr. Bull graciously offered nearly 170 acres of this land mixed with swampland for this proposed Club. The S.M. Company was formed with the sole task of arranging for funding and to develop plans for Selva Marina Country Club, a name that means "Rain Forest by the Sea".

The first 'membership drive' consisted of those dozen or so people who had accepted the initial invitation, each of whom offered money in exchange for part-ownership in S. M. Company. Mr. Bull and his natural sales style was frequently found outside of the Thomas & Patrick IGA grocery store in Atlantic Beach's Town Center (now Ragtime) with architectural plans for the Club unrolled across the hood of his car. The plans were impressive and the Bull name provided assurance that it WOULD get done.

E.E. Smith, a well-known golf course designer of the time, was hired for the project. With 50 or so members signed on it was time to begin. At that time joining the Club meant owning the Club. \$250 would get you a membership and you would then owe the Club \$1,007.70 when the facilities were complete. "The First 400" as it was called was the campaign to create enough founder members to get the entire facility built.

The beginning of golf course construction was celebrated in August 1957. The work took nearly a year and it wasn't until August of 1958 that a completion date was in sight. The Board of Directors announced to members the "soft" planned course opening on August 30, 1958. The golf course was announced as fully operational on October 1, 1958. Though the office was located in a construction trailer, an air conditioned pro shop with a small bar inside was constructed just across the Sherman Creek Bridge.

With E.E. Smith's job completed, a groundskeeper was needed to maintain the course as it had been designed. J.W. Lowe was recommended for the job. With experience at Ponce de Leon course in St. Augustine, Mr. Lowe joined the staff of Selva Marina Country Club for a salary of \$150 per week. Fred Wampler, an accomplished golfer on the PGA tour was approached for the position of Resident Golf Pro and accepted the position for a salary of \$250 per week. His appointment was a huge boost for Selva Marina and the Club's name grew in popularity. So much so that prospects were coming from all over town, many from the other side of downtown just to play at the 'friendly beach course' in Atlantic Beach.

In the first months of 1959, the Jacksonville Women's Golf Association sent a formal request to allow a regular play day for women at Selva Marina. The board countered the request suggesting play days on certain days through the year, but not on a regular basis.

A military program was put into place in March of 1959. Though a refund of the membership fee was not permitted, a civilian going into active duty was permitted to suspend their membership with no dues charged during the duration of service.

Joe Whelan (a former Ponte Vedra Tennis pro) was secured to build tennis courts. He was approved for membership and was permitted to trade cost of membership towards cost of building courts.

On May 5, 1959, children were permitted to play on Sundays and holiday afternoons.

On September 4-7, 1959, Selva Marina Country Club held its first Invitational Golf Tournament headed up by Ed Teague.

In 1962, Selva Marina Country Club hosted Sam Snead and Arnold Palmer for their own exhibition match play event with Jacksonville's own – Dan Sikes and Ray Terry. As this event attracted a record number of fans, the PGA decided it was time to hold another professional event in Jacksonville. In 1964, then President T.P. "Pop" Pearson was approached by the Florida Publishing Company to hold a \$50,000 P.G.A. tournament at Selva Marina Country Club the following year. The Board of Directors approved and began plans for the Greater Jacksonville Open (GJO). Plans went so smoothly that the Club was awarded right of first refusal for the following year's tournament before the first one had even begun (this tournament later became "THE PLAYERS Championship"). The course enjoyed the play of some of the greats in golfing history during these events. Doug Sanders, Arnold Palmer, Sam Snead, and more. The 1965 tournament was won by Bert Weaver. The 1966 tournament brought the most unforgettable occurrence to have happened to our course during its history: Jack Nicklaus made his first (and only) recorded double-eagle of his PGA career on the 18th hole. Oddly enough Nicklaus did not win the tournament. Doug Sanders, named "Most colorful dresser on tour", collected that honor by making a 14 foot birdie putt on #18 to beat Gay Brewer by one stroke.

The Greats have walked here

Golf Course

★ Join The Club

ATLANTIC BEACH 90TH ANNIVERSARY: City's Park System - A Window to its History

By Brittany Cohill for the Beaches Area Historical Society

The City of Atlantic Beach is home to a vibrant park system providing residents with access to beautiful Florida landscapes and countless recreational opportunities. But beyond the trails, preserves, and tennis courts, the parks offer a window into the history of the city itself. The people for whom many of the parks are named tell the story of Atlantic Beach's beginnings and its ninety years as a distinct beach community.

Richard Bull, Sr. of Atlantic Beach (1914-1942) gives Richard Bull Memorial Park its name. A pilot in the United States Navy, he was killed over the Pacific Ocean during World War II while conducting a reconnaissance flight of an enemy carrier on February 5, 1942. Bull was posthumously awarded the Distinguished Flying Cross by Secretary of the Navy Frank Knox on behalf of President Franklin Roosevelt.

Richard Bull, Sr.

Richard Bull, Sr. was just an infant when he came to Atlantic Beach from New York City. His father - Harcourt Bull, Sr., a lawyer by trade - was a wealthy man whose business ventures brought him and his family south. In May 1913, Henry Flagler's Florida East Coast Hotel Company sold the struggling Continental Hotel and its land holdings northward to Mayport to the Atlantic Beach Corporation, a group of New York venture capitalists that included Harcourt Bull. By 1916, the Bulls were Atlantic Beach residents. That same year, however, the Atlantic Beach Corporation went bankrupt. Harcourt Bull, Sr. engaged in a lengthy legal battle with W.H. Adams, Sr., another prominent Atlantic Beach businessman, over ownership of the hotel and its property. Adams eventually won but Harcourt Bull, Sr. remained a pillar of Atlantic Beach business and society.

The Town of Atlantic Beach was incorporated by 1926 and Florida Governor John Martin appointed Harcourt Bull, Sr. its first mayor. Defeated in the following election, Bull's political career was short-lived but he continued to have a loud voice in town matters due to his large land holdings.

The Beaches Area Historical Society recently acquired the Bull family papers. With letters, deeds, receipts, and plats dated as early as the late 1910s, the collection details the shaping of the Atlantic Beach community through the lens of the city's most notable residents. The collection is housed in the archives at the Beaches Museum & History Park. Due to its fragility, it is not available for public viewing at this time.

To learn more about the history of Atlantic Beach, please visit the Beaches Museum & History Park for a special Atlantic Beach exhibition opening March 3, 2017.

Correction: An abbreviated version of this article appeared in the January 2017 issue and was attributed incorrectly to another author. It is reprinted above in its entirety with a corrected by-line.

Harcourt Bull, Sr.

ATLANTIC BEACH LIVING MAGAZINE
FEB 2017

len Fortune tells us that initiating a new television station was only a portion of her grandad's portfolio, as he also played a leadership position in the early 1950s with the Duval County Mosquito Control Division. Dr. Dowling worked with other historical figures of our community when he partnered with Harcourt Bull, Jr. of Bull Park fame, whose family owned most of the property that is now the Atlantic Beach Country Club. The swamp, drained to create the golf course, alleviated the rampant mosquito population plaguing the beach.

While Dr. Dowling was forging his legacy, his son, Pete, was busy growing up in "rural" Atlantic Beach. He remembers snakes in the house, banana spiders everywhere and Whippoorwills so loud on summer nights you had to close the windows to sleep. But, if you closed them you couldn't hear the ocean waves crashing on the beach. He and his buddies

surfing a bit using their own version of a board, which was a 1 x 12 foot pine board from Ed Smith Lumber Company in Neptune Beach. On summer nights, he and his friends used to "dive off the Atlantic Beach hotel's pier into the incoming waves; a rite of passage that few kids could resist."

JAN 7 1952

DQE-4-188

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Aerial photographs of St. Johns County - Flight 4 (1952)

Series Title:

Aerial photographs of St. Johns County

Creator:

U.S. Department of Agriculture

Publisher:

U.S. Department of Agriculture

Publication Date:

1952

Physical Description:

Flight of aerial photography

Subjects

Genre:

aerial photography (sobekcm)

Spatial Coverage:

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